

Supplementary Material S3: 4P Coding Rulebook (Inter-rater $\kappa = 0.87$)

Coding Protocol Summary

Single expert coder (SB: nuclear medicine physicist, >50 PET publications)

25% random audit by second coder (KE: >20 publications)

Discordant cases resolved by discussion → final $\kappa = 0.87$ (95% CI: 0.82-0.92)

Pilot tested on 12 studies prior to full extraction (n=47)

PRODUCT Dimension (Hardware/Tracer Physics) - $\kappa = 0.91$

Code	Criteria	Examples
0	Standard scintillator/no TOF (CRT >450ps)	BGO, LSO (NaI SPECT), older PET
1	LYSO:Ce TOF (385-450ps)	GE Discovery MI, Siemens Vision, Vereos
2	Ultra-fast TOF (<385ps)	uEXPLORER, PennPET, LSO2:Ce

PROCESS Dimension (Reconstruction/Correction) - $\kappa = 0.89$

Code	Reconstruction Algorithm	Motion Correction Method
0	OSEM ($\leq 4i20s$)	None
1	BSREM/Q.Clear ($\beta \leq 50$) OR OSEM ($> 4i20s$)	Phase-based gating
2	BSREM ($\beta > 50$) OR Deep Learning recon	Optical flow OR continuous correction

POSITIONING Dimension (Hybrid Integration) - $\kappa = 0.85$

Code	Attenuation Correction Source	Registration Method
0	PET/CT (CT-based μ -map)	Rigid body
1	PET/MR (MR-based μ -map OR template)	Deformable/non-rigid
2	MR-only μ -map OR Direct ML attenuation	AI-based registration

PARADIGM Dimension (Adaptive Workflow) - $\kappa = 0.82$

Code	Respiratory/Cardiac Gating	Protocol Adaptation
0	None	Fixed dose/time/protocol
1	Phase-based gating	Adaptive dose OR time
2	Amplitude gating OR Data-driven	Real-time dosimetry OR AI-adaptive

Decision Tree for Ambiguous Cases

1. "TOF-enabled" but no timing reported → Code 1 (modern LYSO assumption)
2. "Motion corrected" but method unspecified → Code 1 (phase gating default)
3. Multiple recon algorithms reported → Code highest level present
4. Vendor-specific terms (Q.Clear, FlowMotion) → Map to BSREM equivalent

Audit Results (25% sample, n=12 studies)

- Initial agreement: 87% (104/120 items)
- Post-discussion: 100%
- κ evolution: 0.78 → 0.87 after rulebook refinement

Full coding database: Zenodo DOI:10.5281/zenodo.18745283